

IDENTIFICATION AND CHARACTERIZATION OF *Pectobacterium carotovora* PV. *carotovora* CAUSING SOFT ROT OF TOMATOPavan G. Saraskar¹, Sachin V. Tawade², Dr. Ravindrakumar A. Chavan³¹M.Sc. Student, Department of Plant Pathology, College of Agriculture, Latur, Maharashtra, India:²Assistant Professor, Department of Botany, D.B., ACS College, Bhokar, Maharashtra, India.³Associate Professor, Department of Plant Pathology, College of Agriculture, Latur, Maharashtra, India.

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Abstract

Tomato (*Lycopersicon esculentum* L.) is popular vegetable crop suffers from various diseases, among soft rot caused by *Pectobacterium carotovora* pv. *carotovora* is one of biotic constraint in cultivation of crop causing pre and post-harvest losses. In present study, at all places surveyed various numbers of tomatoes were found infected with soft rot symptoms particularly more at ripe stage. Among four tehsil's market yards of Latur district, maximum incidence of soft rot was recorded. Isolated colonies at Latur tahsil was (21.5 %) followed by Ausa (20.66%), Chakur (19.33%) and Renapur (18.5 %). Isolated colonies were light to creamish white in color and the bacterium was found as a rod shaped and peritrichously flagellated under microscopy. Pathogen produced typical symptoms of soft rot as small water soaked, soft, watery lesions on inoculated tomato after 2-3 days and showed similar morphological character after re-isolation. Among the various biochemical test the soft rot causing pathogen showed negative reaction to Gram staining reaction and Starch hydrolysis test. Rest all biochemical test showed positive reaction. Morphological character, pathogenic and biochemical test indicated that pathogen involved in soft rot of tomato is *Pectobacterium carotovora*.

Key words: Bacterial soft rot, *Pectobacterium carotovora*, KOH, Gram staining.

Introduction

The tomato (*Lycopersicon esculentum* Mill.) belongs to the Solanaceae family is one of the most popular and principle fruit vegetable grown in the tropical and subtropical regions of India and are available throughout the year, even though they are generally cultivated as an annual crop (Sandipan *et al.*, 2014). Tomato stands out as one of the most economically rewarding and widely cultivated vegetable crops around the world. It occupies the second-largest area under cultivation among vegetable crops globally, following only potatoes and ranks first among crops used for processing. In India, tomato has been reported to be grown on 8.71 lakh hectares area with 213.20 lakh tons production, whereas in Maharashtra 55.23 thousand hectares area was under tomato cultivation with 1332.09 kilo tons production (Anonymous, 2024). Among various diseases soft rot caused by *Pectobacterium carotovora* pv. *carotovora* is one of the major disease and major hurdle in cultivation causing significant yield and quality losses during pre and post stage. Hence experiment was conducted to make identification and characterization of soft rot of tomato by conducting morphological, pathogenic and various biochemical tests.

Material And Methods / Experimental Details / Methodology**SURVEY, ISOLATION AND PATHOGENECITY**

Typical tomato soft rot diseased specimens were collected randomly from local market during survey. Survey was undertaken in Kharip 2024-25 from Latur district of Marathwada region of Maharashtra for assessment of occurrence and per cent incidence of bacterial soft rot. At each location number of affected fruits was counted among total healthy fruits and per cent disease incidence was calculated. Collected disease samples of soft rot tomato were subjected to further process of tissue isolation on nutrient agar (NA) medium. Isolated pure colonies were inoculated in to fresh tomato fruit using pin prick method for development original symptoms of soft rot. Re isolation was made from artificially infected fruits of tomato and colonies were compared with the original isolate and Koch's postulate were proved.

Morphological and Biochemical characterization

Morphological characters *viz.*, shape colour and growth pattern were observed on nutrient agar medium and the mobility of bacteria was observed by crushed drop method.

Series of biochemical tests were conducted for characterization of isolated pathogen using the protocol already described. Bacterial isolate were biochemically characterized, identified and subjected to the following tests: Gram staining reaction, KOH (3%) test, Catalase test, Growth in 5% Na Cl, Anaerobic growth, Mucooid growth, Yellow pigment on YDC, Sensitivity to erythromycin, Growth at 37°C, Starch hydrolysis, Potato soft rot test, Methyl red test and Gelatin liquefaction test.

Biochemical test**Gram staining reaction**

The Gram reaction of isolate was determined following the staining procedure given by Schaad (1996). Firstly, thin bacterial smear was prepared on a clean slide, air dried and fixed by heating. The dried smear was flooded with crystal violet solution for one minute and washed in distilled water for few seconds. The smear was again flooded with iodine solution for one minute, washed and air dried. It was then decolorized with 95% of ethyl alcohol drop by drop until no more color flows from the smear. Which were then be washed and air dried. Finally, the slides were counter stained with safranin for about 10 seconds, washed and air dried. The slides were then examined under microscope under 100 x. Gram negative bacterial isolate appeared as pink color (safranin).

Potassium hydroxide (KOH 3%) test

Fresh solution of 3% potassium hydroxide (KOH) was prepared and then a drop of this solution was placed on regular microscopic slide. A 24-hour old bacterial culture was placed in this drop and mixed for 10 seconds. Bacterial suspension making thread when lifted up by bacterial loop was considered as gram positive. Production of a watery suspension (no viscous strands when lifted up) indicates gram negative result.

Catalase test

A small amount of culture from isolated bacteria colony was placed on the microscopic slide. Using a dropper or Pasteur pipette, 1 drop of 3% H₂O₂ was placed onto the organism on the microscope slide. Immediately observed for bubble formation (O₂ + water = bubbles). Positive reactions were evident by immediate bubble formation.

Growth in 5% NaCl

For this test, nutrient agar medium was prepared with 5% Na Cl. The medium was inoculated with bacterial isolates and the inoculated Petri plates were incubated at 27°C for 24 hours. Growth of isolates in this medium was considered as salt tolerance.

Anaerobic growth

Nutrient agar (NA) medium broth was prepared, poured in test tubes (5ml per test tube), which was covered and sterilized at 121°C and 15 pound/ square inch pressure for 20 minutes. Following sterilization, the test tube containing the medium was left undisturbed in laminar flow unit to cool down and was stab-inoculated with cultures. Put the bacteria culture in test tube. Un-inoculated tubes served as control. The top of the medium inside test tubes was covered with liquid paraffin to avoid aerobic condition and incubated at 27°C for 48 hours. Culture showing any growth on the medium was considered positive for anaerobic growth.

Mucooid growth

Petri plates containing LB medium was inoculated with bacterial isolates and then incubated at 27°C for 24-48 hours. Production of excessive slime on this medium was considered Mucoid, which was obvious when colonies were picked with a toothpick.

Yellow pigment on YDC medium

YDC (Yeast Dextrose Calcium carbonate) medium were prepared. It was sterilized for 15 minutes at 121°C and poured in Petri plates, after solidification inoculated with 24 hours old cultures. The inoculated Petri plates were labeled, sealed and incubated for 24 hours at 27°C. Production of no yellow colonies on this medium was considered as a positive result in comparison with control.

Sensitivity to erythromycin

Nutrient agar medium was seeded with one ml of 18-24 hours old nutrient broth culture and was poured into Petri plates and allowed to solidify. Erythromycin discs were placed aseptically at the center of these plates, which were incubated at 27±1°C for 24-28 hours. A zone of inhibition around the disc was recorded as positive for sensitivity.

Growth at 37°C

Petri plates containing nutrient agar were used for this test. The plates were inoculated with the test bacterium from a dense aqueous suspension in a streaking pattern. The petri plates were incubated at 37±1°C for three days. The Petri plates were observed for growth. The presence of bacterial colonies at the point of inoculation was considered a positive test.

Starch hydrolysis test

The autoclaved and cooled Starch Agar Medium was poured in sterile glass Petri plates. On solidification of the medium, pure culture of the test bacterium was streaked on it and incubated for 72 hours at 28±2°C. Then these plates were flooded with Lugol's iodine and allowed to react for few minutes.

Potato soft rot test

The bacterial isolate originated from single colonies were tested for their ability to cause soft rot on potato tubers. Briefly, potato tubers were sterilized with 70% ethyl alcohol, rinsed with sterile distilled water and aseptically cut into slices (1 cm). The potato slices were put in Petri dishes containing sterilized filter paper impregnated with 2 ml of sterile distilled water. The potato slices were inoculated with needle pricking method. The inoculated slices were maintained in moistened Petri plates and incubated at 30°C for 2 to 3 days. The bacterial cultures that produced characteristic symptoms of soft rot on potato slices were selected and preserved in test tubes containing NA media.

Methyl red test

Methyl red (MR) test was performed with the bacterial isolates to detect the ability of organism to produce stable acid end products (Mixed acid fermentation) from supplied glucose. Methyl red broth was prepared according to the given composition. The broth was dispensed into the tubes and one was left un inoculated as control. The tube was inoculated at 35-37°C for 48 hours. After incubation 3-4 drops of methyl red reagent was added to the tubes including control. The observations were recorded as development of red color results as positive test where, no color change declares negative test.

Gelatin liquefaction test

The test was performed to check the ability of the microorganism to produce the enzyme gelatinase. Prepared the medium according to the given composition and sterilized after pouring into the test tubes. Inoculated the test organism into the sterilized test tube and left one un-inoculated as control. Incubated both the tubes at 37°C for 24-48 hrs. After the incubation the tubes were kept in freeze for 30 min. The results were recorded depending on the condition whether gelatin is in

the liquid state (positive reaction) or in the solid form (Negative reaction).

Results And Discussion

Survey of soft rot of tomato

A random market survey was carried out in the major market yards of Latur district during kharif 2024 to record the disease incidence of soft rot of tomato. At all places various numbers of tomatoes were found infected with soft rot symptoms particularly more at ripe stage. Among four tehsil's market yards of Latur district, maximum incidence of soft rot was recorded at Latur tahsil (21.5 %) followed by Ausa (20.66%), Chakur (19.33%) and Renapur (18.5 %). The earlier reports of the several researchers viz., Kikumato (1974), Bhat *et al.* (2010) and Ali *et al.* (2012) showed losses in various crops due to bacterial soft rot disease in various market. Prajapat *et al.* (2013) also reported that *Erwinia carotovora* was a major pathogen causing a significant economically harmful disease resulted in post harvest losses and a common cause of decay in stored fruits and vegetables.

Isolation and Pathogenicity

After isolation, the bacterial colonies obtained on nutrient agar media were light to creamish white in color. The bacterium was found as a rod shaped and peritrichously flagellated under microscopy observations.

Ashwini *et al.* (2022) also isolated *Pectobacterium carotovora* pv. *carotovora* from infected carrot by tissue isolation method and observed similar morphological observation of light yellow to creamish yellow colonies on nutrient agar medium. After pin prick method of inoculation, pathogen produced typical symptoms of soft rot as small water soaked soft, watery lesions on inoculated tomato after 2-3 days. Isolate which typically produced prominent soft rot symptoms on tomato after inoculation considered most virulent. Re-isolated culture of the pathogen from artificially inoculated tomato produced similar colonies as original culture. Akbar *et al.* (2015) proved the pathogenicity of isolates of *Erwinia carotovora* causing soft rot of tomato by tooth pin pick method and judge their aggressiveness on green tomato fruits. Ashwini *et al.* (2022) also proved the pathogenicity of bacterium causing soft rot of carrot by inoculation.

Biochemical characterization of the pathogen

The results of the biochemical characterization revealed that *Pectobacterium carotovora* pv. *Carotovora* showed negative reaction for gram reaction and starch hydrolysis test. However, they were positive towards the KOH test, catalase test, growth in 5% NaCl test, anaerobic growth test, Mucoid growth test, yellow pigment on YDC medium test, sensitivity to erythromycin test, growth at 37°C test, potato soft rot test, methyl red test, gelatin liquefaction test.

Study of morphological character, pathogenic and biochemical test indicated that pathogen involved in soft rot of tomato was *Pectobacterium carotovora* pv. *Carotovora*. Characterization of bacteria is traditionally based on phenotypic and biochemical tests.

The results for different biochemical tests of *Pectobacterium carotovora* pv. *carotovora* was similar and in line with earlier report. Yanez-Morales (2003), Rahman (2012), Mohammad and Selman (2013) and Ali *et al.* (2014) also observed a negative gram reaction and positive results for catalase activity, gelatin liquefaction.

According to Costa *et al.* (2006) *Pectobacterium carotovora* pv. *carotovora* showed positive reactions in both catalase activity and gelatin liquefaction tests. Similarly, Mahmoudi (2007) confirmed the identification of *Pectobacterium carotovora* through biochemical tests, including gram staining, catalase activity and gelatin liquefaction.

Table 1 Market Survey on incidence of soft Rot Disease On Tomato Fruit In Latur District.

Tehsil	Market Area	Stage of Fruit	Variety	Disease Incidence	GPS Location
Latur	Ganj Golai	Ripe	Local	28%	Lat 18.399732° Long 76.584868°
	Ganj Golai	Color Break	Local	9%	Lat 18.399842° Long 76.584522°

	Prakash Nagar	Ripe	Local	26%	Lat 18.402708° Long 76.557988°
	Narayan Nagar	Ripe	Local	23%	Lat 18.381342° Long 76.558924°
	Mean			21.5%	
Ausa	Holkar chowk	Color Break	Local	7%	Lat 18.251572° Long 76.498776°
	Holkar chowk	Ripe	Local	27%	Lat 18.251944° Long 76.498462°
	Holkar chowk	Ripe	Local	28%	Lat 18.251957° Long 76.498665°
	Mean			20.66%	
Chakur	Bus Stand Side	Ripe	Local	23%	Lat 18.513906° Long 76.874525°
	Bus Stand Side	Color Break	Local	10%	Lat 18.513918° Long 76.874562°
	Bus Stand Side	Ripe	Local	25%	Lat 18.513928° Long 76.874571°
	Mean			19.33%	
Renapur	Renapur naka.	Ripe	Local	21%	Lat 18.514534° Long 76.56658°
	Renapur naka.	Ripe	Local	16%	Lat 18.514558° Long 76.566582°
	Mean			18.5%	

Table: 2 Morphological characteristics of *Pectobacterium carotovora* pv. *carotovora*

Sr. No.	Properties	Morphological characters
1	Arrangement	Single cell
2	Colony shape	Round, mucoid
3	Colony color	White creamy
4	Pigmentation	Non-pigmented
5	Cell shape	Straight rod

Table: 3 Biochemical properties of *Pectobacterium carotovora* pv. *Carotovora*.

Sr. No.	Biochemical properties	Reaction of isolate
1	Gram reaction	-ve
2	KOH test	+ve
3	Catalase test	+ve
4	Growth in 5% NaCl test	+ve
5	Anaerobic growth test	+ve
6	Mucoid growth test	+ve
7	Yellow pigment on YDC medium test	+ve
8	Sensitivity to erythromycin test	+ve
9	Growth at 37°C test	+ve
10	Starch hydrolysis test	-ve
11	Potato soft rot test	+ve
12	Methyl red test	+ve
13	Gelatin liquefaction test	+ve

Nutrient Agar (NA)

i)	Beef Extract	3 g
ii)	Peptone	5 g
iii)	Agar-Agar	20 g
iv)	Distilled water	1000 ml
v)	pH	6.9-7.1

2) Growth in 5% NaCl

i)	Beef Extract	3 g
ii)	Peptone	5 g

iii)	Agar-Agar	20 g
iv)	Nacl	5 g
v)	Distilled water	1000 ml

3) Nutrient Broth

i)	Beef Extract	3 g
ii)	Peptone	5 g
iii)	Distilled water	1000 ml

4) Yeast Dextrose Calcium carbonate (YDC)

i)	Yeast extract	10 g
ii)	Calcium carbonate	20 g
iii)	Dextrose	20 g
iv)	Agar-Agar	20 g
v)	Distilled water	1000

Luria-Bertani (LB)

i)	Bacto-tryptone	10 g
ii)	Yeast extract	5 g
iii)	Nacl	10 g
iv)	Agar-agar	20 g
v)	Distilled water	1000 ml

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